

SUBDUCTION-RELATED ARC MAGMATISM VERSUS POST-COLLISIONAL MAGMATISM, A DISCUSSION

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This presentation will provide a series of information on the similarities and differences between “arc volcanism” and “post-collisional” volcanism on a global scale.

Subduction-related arc magmatism or simply arc are chains of volcanoes on the overthrust plate parallel to, an 100–200 km horizontally away from, the surface expression of a subduction zone, together with coeval, underlying plutonic rocks. The magmatism is dominant subalkaline magmatic rocks and the source is in the mantle at the level of subducted lithosphere. The best expression of these volcanic chains is presently in the Pacific area along North and South America, or Japan to New Zealand.

Fig. 1 Subduction-related arc magmatism

Post-collisional magmatism shows a systematic pattern of temporal variation of the magmatism that act as a major indicator of source evolution: acidic ignimbrite flare-up is at the inception, followed by a variety of subalkaline, potassic or ultrapotassic magmas suggesting a dehydration and “de-fertilization” of the lithospheric mantle source. The latest magmas are mainly sodic alkaline in composition, suggesting a transition from lithosphere to asthenosphere melting in the orogenic environment. The characteristic area for this environment is Alpine–Himalayan belt. An example of such kind is the Călimani-Gurghiu-Harghita (CGH) volcanic chain (see below in Fig. 2 an interpretative cross-section through the post-collisional environment of the CGH, including magmatic system after Mațenco et al., (2010)).

Fig. 2 Interpretative cross-section through the post-collisional environment of the CGH

The main conclusion is that subduction-related arc magmatism compared with post-collisional magmatism shows different relationships between magmatic and tectonic processes.

References

Mañenco L., Krézsek C., Merten S., Schmid S., Cloetingh S., Andriessen P. (2010). Characteristics of collisional orogens with low topographic build-up: an example from the Carpathians. *Terra Nova* 22, 155–165